

**Role of dietary supplements in treatment and prophylaxis of COVID-19: A Systematic
Review**

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Abstract

Coronaviruses are a family of viruses known to infect mammals and birds, belonging to the family Coronaviridae. Before the emergence of COVID-19, there were six different coronaviruses known to infect humans, four of which cause a mild common cold-type illness. The main objective of the study is to review the role of dietary supplements in treatment and prophylaxis of COVID-19. This study was conducted using a systematic search on Google scholar, Pubmed and Web of science published until 20th June 2020. The cited references of retrieved articles and previous reviews were also manually checked to identify any additional eligible studies. All citations were imported into a bibliographic database and duplicates were removed. Title, abstract and then full-text of all articles were screened for eligibility. Vitamin D has important functions beyond those of calcium and bone metabolism that include

modulation of the innate and adaptive immune responses. At least 1 billion people globally have vitamin D deficiency. Vitamin D deficiency and insufficiency makes our population more vulnerable and more susceptible to develop infectious diseases especially respiratory infections. It is concluded that the research has yet not proved that vitamin D is effective against the novel Corona virus, it does show that vitamin D helps to protect against respiratory tract infections.

Key words: COVID-19, Nutrition, Dietary, Supplement

Introduction

In December 2019, a virus named ‘‘Severe acute respiratory syndrome corona virus-2’’ (SARS-COV-2 or COVID-19) infected people in China causing fever, dry cough, shortness of breath and pneumonia. Virus can be transmitted from one human to another. Now this mass killer infection is a pandemic around the world. Coronaviruses are important pathogens to animals and humans and have been around for many years. Severe acute respiratory syndrome was first detected in Guangdong in southern China in 2002 and the Middle East respiratory syndrome followed and first emerged in Saudi Arabia in 2012. Both result in severe respiratory infections, which can be fatal¹. In late December 2019 a further coronavirus emerged, severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2), resulting in the potentially fatal COVID-19 disease. This novel coronavirus has rapidly become a global public health concern, spreading to most countries worldwide².

Coronaviruses are a family of viruses known to infect mammals and birds, belonging to the family Corona viridae. Before the emergence of COVID-19, there were six different coronaviruses known to infect humans, four of which cause a mild common cold-type illness. The remaining two coronaviruses emerged in 2002 and 2012 and result in a more severe disease in humans³. These were named severe acute respiratory syndrome (SARS) and the

Middle East respiratory syndrome (MERS) and are highly pathogenic viruses. Both SARS and MERS are believed to have originated in bats, suggesting animal to human transmission⁴.

Unfortunately, no vaccines against coronaviruses have ever been developed, including for SARS or MERS, with MERS still remaining largely uncontrolled. Similarly, there is no single specific antiviral therapy⁵. The ramification of SARS-CoV-2 is atypical viral pneumonia, with the main treatment strategy of supportive care, which may include oxygen or artificial ventilation. Antibiotics are of no use to treat viral pneumonia. The fatality rates in China (and now Italy) follow a distinct pattern, with the elderly having the highest death and case fatality rate⁶.

Most public health strategies being employed are currently reactive. However, immune nutrition could have an important preventative role a form of 'prehabilitation' helping the body to cope with potentially lethal viruses such as coronavirus⁷. Elsewhere, prehabilitation has been defined as 'interventions that can help to improve patient's health in advanced of being exposed to a physiological stressor so they are then better able to cope with that stress'. It is known that viral clearance and infection recovery require activation of the host's immune response, and nutrition could be a means of achieving this⁸.

Figure 01: Sever acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2 (SARS-CoV-2) virus uses the angiotensin converting enzyme 2 (ACE2) receptor to enter the host cell and the trans membrane protease serine 2 (TMPRSS2) for Spike (S) protein priming.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to review the role of dietary supplements in treatment and prophylaxis of COVID-19.

Methodology of the study

This study was conducted using a systematic search on Google scholar, Pubmed and Web of science published until 20th June 2020. The cited references of retrieved articles and previous reviews were also manually checked to identify any additional eligible studies.

Data collection

All citations were imported into a bibliographic database and duplicates were removed. Title, abstract and then full-text of all articles were screened for eligibility. All the studies which was

directly included the role of dietary supplements were included in this study. The following information was extracted from each study: a) details of the study (study setting, year of publication and study design), b) study population, sample size (male/female) and age of the subjects in years, c) primary intervention(s) and control group and d) which dietary supplement is explained in the study. These are reported in the relevant tables for vitamins, minerals, nutraceutical and probiotics, for comparison of similar outcomes between interventions. Differential percentages of each vitamin-related study, differential percentages of studies about the association with COVID-19 and mechanisms of vitamins' effects on the immune system for every vitamin were also reviewed.

Figure 02: Anti-inflammatory effect of bioactive compounds present in foodstuffs.

Figure 03: Flow of information through the different phases of a systematic review.

Results

There were total 188 studies that identified initially from PubMed, Google scholar and Web of Science databases. After excluding duplicates and articles that did not meet the inclusion criteria, we obtained 90 articles with full-texts which were read for further evaluation, where another 75 were excluded as irrelevant. Overall, we included 15 articles that directly match on the inclusion criteria.

Table 01: Dietary supplements in treatment and prophylaxis of COVID-19

Author; Published Year	Dietary supplement	Study design	Study population	Outcomes
Patel et al., 2019 ⁸	Vit- A and D	Randomized control study	Children (2-8 years)	Higher antibody responses among children who entered the study with insufficient or deficient levels of RBP and 25- hydroxyvitamin D.
Kathleen et al., 2020 ⁹	Vitamin C, vitamin D, zinc, elderberry, and silver.	Clinical trials	COVID-19 patients	Zinc supplements for the common cold have conflicted, and many suffer from methodological flaws.
Alfredo et al., 2020 ¹⁰	Relationship among nutrition, the immune system, and	Randomized control study	COVID-19 patients	Optimal intake of all nutrients, mainly those playing crucial roles in immune system, should be assured

	coronavirus disease.			through a diverse and well-balanced diet.
Rashmi et al., 2020 ¹¹	Role of Vitamin-D	Review analysis	COVID-19 patients	People at risk of COVID-19 may be considered for vitamin D supplementation.
Amit et al., 2020 ¹²	Potential role of zinc supplementation in prophylaxis and treatment of COVID-19	Hypothetical study	COVID-19 patients	Zn supplementation may be of potential benefit for prophylaxis and treatment of COVID-19.
Joseph et al., 2020 ¹³	vitamin D3 supplementation over weeks to months may prevent other acute respiratory infections, particularly in people with low or very low vitamin D status	Clinical trials	COVID-19 patients	Clinicians should treat patients with vitamin D deficiency irrespective of any link with respiratory infection.

F. M. Panfili et al., 2020 ¹⁴	Possible role of vitamin D in Covid-19 infection in pediatric population	Review analysis	Pediatric population	Vitamin D proved to interact both with the innate immune system, by activating Toll-like receptors (TLRs)
William et al., 2020 ¹⁵	Vitamin D Supplementation Could Reduce Risk of Influenza and COVID-19 Infections and Deaths	Randomized controlled trial	COVID-19 patients	Treatment of people who become infected with COVID-19, higher vitamin D ₃ doses might be useful.
Adrian et al., 2020 ¹⁶	Chloroquine for Treatment or Prophylaxis of COVID-19	Hypothetical analysis	COVID-19 patients	Evidence on the benefits and harms of using hydroxychloroquine or chloroquine to treat COVID-19 is very weak and conflicting.
Giovanni et al., 2020 ¹⁷	Functional Role of Dietary Intervention to Improve the Outcome of COVID-19	Hypothetical analysis	COVID-19 patients	Dietary constituents can be used to improve the patients' outcomes during lung infection, regulating the

				inflammatory response.
Christianne et al., 2020 ¹⁸	Dietary recommendations during the COVID-19 pandemic	Review analysis	COVID-19 patients	Guidance related to the safe handling of food, from production to consumption, is critical to reduce the risk of viral dissemination.
ABRAN et al., 2020 ¹⁹	Most-relevant vitamins and minerals: vitamin A, vitamin C, vitamin D, zinc (vegetarians may need up to 50% more dietary zinc than nonvegetarians), selenium;	Review analysis	COVID-19 patients	Supplementation with vitamins, minerals, and probiotics does not treat or prevent COVID-19 infection, but it can optimize the immune response, acting as an adjunct treatment.
Dietitians of Canada., 2020 ²⁰	Consume a healthy diet rich in fruit and vegetables, protein foods, and whole grains	Review analysis	COVID-19 patients	There is no evidence that COVID-19 is spread through eating or touching raw fruits or vegetables

EUFIC., 2020 ²¹	Appropriate intakes of copper, folate, iron, selenium, zinc, and vitamins A, B ₆ , B ₁₂ , C, and D play an important role in the immune system	Review analysis	COVID-19 patients	Supplements can be used to add nutrients to the diet in individuals who have specific challenges in meeting dietary requirements
UNICEF., 2020 ²²	Maintain fruit and vegetable intake; Choose healthy dried or canned alternatives when fresh produce is not available.	Review analysis	Pediatric population	Breast milk remains an optimal food for infants and children aged 6 to 24 months

Vitamin D has important functions beyond those of calcium and bone metabolism that include modulation of the innate and adaptive immune responses. At least 1 billion people globally have vitamin D deficiency. Vitamin D deficiency and insufficiency makes our population more vulnerable and more susceptible to develop infectious diseases especially respiratory infections. Until a COVID-19 vaccine or a therapeutic agent is discovered, we can use vitamin D as an adjuvant for both treatment and prevention of respiratory tract infections like COVID-19. The beneficial effect of vitamin D supplementation as an adjuvant in COVID-19 can be due to a combination of anti-infective, immune modulatory and anti-inflammatory effects²³.

Discussion

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first systematic review reporting nutritional interventions to enhance immunity in viral infections taking into consideration the current epidemic of COVID-19. This comprehensive review reports evidence on several vitamins, particularly A, D and E, as well as few trace elements, such as zinc and selenium. Furthermore, a large number of nutraceuticals and several probiotics have also shown immune enhancing effects for either preventing or treating viral infections, especially influenza-like illnesses²⁴.

Several vitamins are essential for the proper functioning of the immune system. A well balanced and varied diet is essential not only to minimize vitamin deficiencies, but also to avoid unnecessary excess consumption or supplementation. According to our findings, vitamin supplementation, especially vitamin D may be beneficial in people who are either deficient or insufficient²⁵. Theoretically, vitamin E is a potent antioxidant and has an ability to modulate the host immune functions. However, most of studies in our review reported adverse effects of vitamin E supplementation on the immune response. Similarly, evidence does not support supplementation of vitamin E in cardiovascular disease and cancer prevention. In fact, high-dosage of vitamin E supplementation may increase all-cause mortality²⁶. Similar to vitamins, several trace elements are essential for proper immune functions. A disrupted zinc homeostasis affects immune cells by several mechanisms leading to abnormal lymphopiesis, disturbed intercellular communication via cytokines, and poor innate host defense via phagocytosis and oxidative burst. Similarly selenium has a complex immunological mechanism but mainly through its incorporation into selenoproteins²⁷.

Role of Specific Dietary Nutrients on Immune System Function and COVID-19 Disease

The influence of nutrition in the immune system has been widely reported. In addition, recent studies have also highlighted the influence of both, an adequate nutritional status and the appropriate intake of specific nutrients in COVID-19. Nevertheless, due to the novelty of the disease, information regarding the effects of some nutrients is scarce, and in some cases, this information comes from ecological studies. Therefore, it seems plausible that part of the information included in this section may be updated in the upcoming months as the result of the research that is currently ongoing²⁸. Protein deficiency is linked to impaired immune system function, mainly due to its negative effects on both, the amount of functional immunoglobulins and gut-associated lymphoid tissue (GALT). Besides quantity, the quality of proteins is also an important factor with regard to the relationship of this macronutrient with immune system. In this line, it has been highlighted that including proteins of high biological value (those present in eggs, lean meat, fish, and dairy) containing all the essential amino acids may exert an anti-inflammatory effect²⁹. In addition, some amino acids, such as arginine and glutamine are well known for their ability to modulate the immune system³⁰.

Conclusion

It is concluded that the research has yet not proved that vitamin D is effective against the novel Corona virus, it does show that vitamin D helps to protect against respiratory tract infections. Vitamin D may have a role to play in suppressing the cytokine storm and thereby reducing the morbidity and mortality due to COVID-19.

Conflict of interest:

There is no conflict of interest.

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